

First confirmed locality record of *Gypogyna forceps* Simon, 1900 (Araneae: Salticidae: Salticinae: Scopocirini) from Paraguay

Brogan L. Pett¹

¹ Colección Científica Para La Tierra, Fundación Para La Tierra, 321 Mariscal Estigarribia, Pilar, Ñeembucú, Paraguay, *email* brogan@paralatierra.org, brogan.pett@outlook.com

Abstract. The first confirmed locality record for *Gypogyna forceps* Simon, 1900 (Salticidae: Scopocirini) is reported from Paraguay, from the southwestern Ñeembucú department. Commentary is provided on the significance of the specimen, and an updated map of the distribution of this species in South America is provided.

Keywords. distribution record, Ñeembucú

The salticid genus *Gypogyna* Simon, 1900 was described from specimens in Paraguay without any locality information other than country. Currently the genus contains only a single described species, *G. forceps* Simon, 1900, with knowledge of another potential but undescribed species from Mexico (Maddison, 2015). *Gypogyna forceps* was redescribed by Galiano (1958) from material collected in Misiones Province in Argentina. Bedoya-Róqueme et al. (2018) provided the northernmost records of this species from Córdoba department, Colombia. This species is also known from Mato Grosso do Sul, in Brazil (Raizer, 2004). Here I present the first confirmed locality record of *G. forceps* in Paraguay, from a male collected at Estancia Santa Ana, Ñeembucú, in southwestern Paraguay. I also report a confirmed observation from Parque Nacional El Palmar, Entre Ríos in eastern Argentina (Roget, 2017). *Gypogyna forceps* is now known from Argentina (Misiones, Entre Ríos), Brazil (Mato Grosso do Sul), Colombia (Córdoba) and Paraguay (Ñeembucú) (Figure 1).

Methods. A single male specimen was examined with an AmScope SZM- stereo microscope, photographs were taken with an AmScope MU1003 10MP digital camera, using the “Extended Depth of Focus” photo stacking method, and identified using the description of Galiano (1958) and the updated diagnosis of Bedoya-Róqueme et al. (2018).

Salticidae: Salticinae: Scopocirini: *Gypogyna forceps* Simon, 1900

Material examined. 1♂, CIPLT-Ar 240, S26.843446°, W58.035986°, Estancia Santa Ana, Ñeembucú, PARAGUAY, 14 SEP 2019, 09:28, “travelling across fence post”, coll. by Marion Richardot. This specimen was deposited in the Colección Científica Para La Tierra (CCPLT) in Pilar, Paraguay.

Figures 1-4. 1, Distribution of *Gypogyna forceps* in South America. *G. forceps* was originally described from Paraguay without locality information. 2-4, ♂ *G. forceps* specimen from Paraguay (CIPLT-Ar 240). 2, Habitus. 3, Dorsomedial to prolateral view of left pedipalp. 4, Ventral (distal segments beginning with tibia) to retrolateral (proximal segments) view of left pedipalp. Map (1) courtesy of mapswire.com (<https://mapswire.com>), adapted under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license.

Diagnosis. Male. Strongly enlarged chelicerae with two teeth on the retromargin, two longitudinal brown bands that extend two-thirds of the length of the abdomen behind the anterior margin, diverging toward the rear where the abdomen is widest, and two dorsolateral black spots to the rear of these bands (Figure 2). Disciform tegulum with a very long embolus, traversing the circumference around the outside twice before curving around the back of the cymbium (Figures 3-4).

Comments. This is the first specimen of *Gypogyna forceps* with a known locality in Paraguay, as the type series was only labeled as "Paraguay." This also marks the first record of this species in Paraguay in 119 years, since the original description. Included here is a second new distribution record based on photographs posted on iNaturalist, from Entre Ríos in Argentina (Roget 2017). This specimen matches, morphologically, the characters associated with the distinctive *G. forceps*. The possibility of an undescribed species of *Gypogyna* from Mexico (Maddison 2015) makes it likely that other species exist within the genus in South America. Much more work will be needed to determine the distribution of *Gypogyna*.

Acknowledgments

I thank the staff at Fundación Para La Tierra, namely Karina Atkinson and Paul Smith, for their support of this project. I also thank Marion Richardot for capture of the specimen, and the Ministerio del Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible (MADES) for issuing relevant research permits.

References

- Bedoya-Róqueme, E., W. Galvis and L. Martínez. 2018.** First record of the genus *Gypogyna* Simon, 1900 (Araneae: Salticidae: Scopocirini) from Colombia. *Peckhamia* 161.1: 1-4.
- Galiano, M. E. 1958.** Novedades sobre los géneros *Scopocira* Simon y *Gypogyna* Simon (Araneae, Salticidae). *Revista de la Sociedad Entomológica Argentina* 20: 21-32.
- Roget, L. 2017.** Research grade observation of *Gypogyna forceps*, online at <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/16019503>, accessed 19 SEP 2019.
- Maddison, W. 2015.** A phylogenetic classification of jumping spiders (Araneae: Salticidae). *Journal of Arachnology*. 43: 231-292.
- Raizer, J., A. D. Brescovit, A.D., U. de Oliveira and A. J. Santos. 2017.** Diversidade e composição da araneofauna do Mato Grosso do Sul, Brasil (Diversity and composition of the spider fauna of Mato Grosso do Sul, Brazil). *Iheringia, Série Zoologia* 107 (supl e2017109): 1-9.
- Simon, E. 1900.** Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux de la famille des Attidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 44: 381-407.